

both the plant and the cups. Ten adult insects were simultaneously released in each treatment. The upper end of the chimney was covered with fine nylon netting. Mortality was recorded at 12 and 24 hours after insect release.

Disulfoton and MIPC were effective fumigants in both dry and wet forms (see table). Application of their granular forms to paddy water can give good field control of BPH. ■

Ovicidal action of insecticides on brown planthopper eggs

P. R. M. Rao and P. S. Prakasa Rao, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRRI), Cuttack, Orissa, India

The brown planthopper (BPH) is an important rice pest, particularly of high yielding varieties. Because the insect thrusts its eggs into the tissues of rice leaf sheaths, insecticidal contact is difficult. Satisfactory control can be achieved only by spraying a persistent insecticide with ovicidal action.

Laboratory experiments to determine the effectiveness of various insecticides and treatments against BPH eggs laid in the leaf sheath were conducted at CRRRI (see table).

Five gravid females were caged overnight on potted plants of TN1 for oviposition. Aqueous solutions of 11 commercial insecticidal preparations were applied as foliar sprays at 0.05% concentration. Sixteen granular insecticides were broadcast at 2.0 kg a.i./ha (calculated by taking the diameter of

Effects of insecticides applied as foliar spray, paddy water broadcast application, and into the root zone on hatching of 1-, 3-, and 5-day-old brown planthopper eggs. Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India, 11–20 April 1977.

Insecticide	Hatching ^a of eggs as affected by								
	Foliar spray (0.05%)			Application at 2 kg a.i./ha into					
				Standing (paddy) water			Root zone		
	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5
Carbofuran	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
Carbaryl	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
Quinalphos	H	H	A	H	H	H	H	H	H
Chlorpyrifos	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
Monocrotophos	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
Chlordimeform	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
Endrin	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
Phosphamidon	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
Dimethoate	-	-	-	H	H	H	H	H	H
BPMC	-	-	-	A	A	A	A	A	A
MIPC	-	-	-	A	A	A	A	A	A
Ac, 92, 100	-	-	-	H	H	H	H	H	H
Fensulfthion	-	-	-	H	H	H	H	H	H
Carbaryl + lindane	-	-	-	H	H	H	H	H	H
Mephosfolan	-	-	-	H	H	H	H	H	H
Endosulfan	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
Lindane	-	-	-	H	H	H	H	H	H
Chlorfenvinphos	-	-	-	H	H	H	H	H	H
Diazinon	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H
Phorate	-	-	-	H	H	H	H	H	H

^a A = abnormal hatching, H = normal hatching, - = not tested; max temp, 34.4°C, min temp, 22.2°C; mean max temp, 33.7°C, mean min temp, 24.3°C, mean RH, 74%.

Abnormal: Fully developed eggs with eye spots, 6 days after oviposition, pierced through the leaf sheath. At this stage, they are dying. In normal hatching, 1st-instar nymphs emerged 6 days after oviposition.

the pot) on the soil surface of the pot to simulate paddy water application. Sixteen granular insecticides were dropped directly in holes made near the rice plants to simulate root-zone placement. Each rice plant had 1-, 3-, and 5-day-old BPH eggs. The control was an untreated plant with BPH eggs. The experiment was replicated three times. The treated plants were observed

for ovicidal action (hatching or nonhatching of eggs) for 10 days.

Carbofuran applied by any method, carbaryl as foliar spray, and BPMC and MIPC applied into standing paddy water or placed in the root zone caused the ultimate death of all eggs before normal hatching. But quinalphos as a foliar spray inhibited normal hatching of 5-day-old eggs only. ■

Soil-incorporated carbofuran for control of rice whorl maggots and "early" stem borers

Gregorio V. Bautista, Aniceto Bautista, and Antonio H. Cruz, Philippine Bureau of Agricultural Extension (BAEx); E. A. Heinrichs, International Rice Research Institute (IRRI); Reeshon Feuer, IRRI-National Crop Protection Center-National Food and Agriculture Council-BAEx, Philippines

Rice seedling damage caused by the rice whorl maggot *Hydrellia* sp. during the first month after transplanting has increased steadily in the Philippines in the past 10 years. Most insecticidal

sprays only partially control the pest. Granular forms of carbofuran or diazinon control the insect reasonably well where water management is good but control it poorly where rains wash the granules off the paddy. Soaking of seedling roots in solutions of granular or flowable (F) carbofuran is effective for 20 to 25 days after transplanting, but is time-consuming and messy. With F the method may be risky for those handling the solution.

IRRI field trials in the 1977 wet season with soil-incorporated granular carbofuran gave excellent control of all

insects, except brown planthopper (BPH), on the susceptible varieties IR22 and TN1 for as long as 50 days after transplanting. Control of BPH lasted 25 days.

BAEX extension specialists implemented evaluation trials with different rates of soil-incorporated granular carbofuran in farmers' fields in the 1978 wet season. They used BPI Ri-4, a new 113-day Bureau of Plant Industry rice variety (selection MRC603-303, from the cross C12// Sigadis/TN1//IR424 (Masagana 99 Group II).